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COGNITIVE STYLISTIC AND PRAGMATIC ASPECTS OF SEMANTIC DEVIATIONS IN THE NOVEL "THE CATCHER IN THE RYE" BY J.D. SALINGER

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the pragmatic and cognitive stylistic analysis of semantic deviations in the novel "The Catcher in the Rye" written by Jerome David Salinger. It goes without saying that in literary works a language tends to have immense meaning since the author has unlimited freedom to communicate his/her ideas in his literary works. This allows a writer to make full use of his creativity to convey his/her message towards the readers by applying his individual style. Semantic deviation is one of the linguistic deviations which is implemented when a combination of incompatible and illogical words violates literary norms of a language in an attempt to evoke a reader's surprise, grab a reader's attention, exert emotional effect and bring aesthetic beauty to a literary text. On top of that, very few investigations have been carried out to research cognitive-stylistic characteristics along with pragmatic characteristics of semantic deviations as key mechanisms of foregrounding and thus this can be an attempt to fill this gap. The language in use will be analyzed in an attempt to study "the meaning of language in relation to a context and of use and users" (Verdonk and Weber, 1995:13). Therefore, it becomes apparent that cognitive aspects and pragmatic aspects go hand in hand and in order to conduct effective research both aspects have to be and will be taken into account.

Keywords: linguistic deviations, stylistic devices, defamiliarization, Grice's matrix, pragmatics.

The article focuses on the cognitive-stylistic and pragmatic aspects of semantic deviations in the novel "The Catcher in the Rye" by J. D. Salinger. Foregrounding occurs when a writer deliberately moves language means to the forefront to make them more noticeable and distinct against the background of language norms and the context. It is possible to distinguish two types of foregrounding that are parallelism and deviation. One of the ultimate goals of foregrounding is to place an emphasis on certain parts of a literary text, to evoke interest, maintain concentration and to induce a reader to decode the implicit meaning. The concept "foregrounding" was first put forward by the pioneers and representatives of Prague School by J. Mukarowski and B. Havranka. The first term, which was proposed by J. Mukarzhovsky, was "aktualisace" (actualization), which was later on translated by P. Garvin as "foregrounding" into English and "выдвижение" into Russian. Initially, the concept "foregrounding" as an integral part of a literary text was put forward by V.B. Shklovsky in the article "Искусство как прием", who is the representative of Russian Formalist school. The term which was proposed by Shklovsky in the article "Искусство как прием" was "остранение", which derives from the word "странный", which can be related to the fact that anything that doesn't conform with language norms tends to be perceived as odd and abnormal. V.B. Shklovsky (1919:105) stresses that "the technique of art is the technique 'остранение' of things and the technique of a difficult form, which results in complexity and boosts length of perception since the perception process in art is the main objective and must be extended; art is a way to experience the making of a thing, and what is done in art is not important."

Semantic deviation falls into the category of the linguistic deviations which is implemented when a

writer deliberately breaches language norms by utilizing incompatible and illogical words in an attempt to trigger reader's attention and exert an aesthetic effect on a reader. According to Leech (1969: 42-52), it is possible to distinguish lexical, grammatical, phonological, graphological semantic, dialectal deviations, deviation of register, and deviation of historical period. Stylistic devices such as metaphor, metonymy, pun, synecdoche etc. are normally deployed to implement semantic deviations, which enable a writer to place certain information that violates language norms to the forefront in an attempt to exert an emotional impact on a reader.

Having revealed the information about foregrounding and semantic deviations, the topicality of the investigation becomes apparent which is connected with the study of the cognitive aspects of semantic deviations or how semantic deviations influence a reader's perception. The ultimate objective of this investigation is to analyze cognitive stylistic and pragmatic characteristics of semantic deviations as key mechanisms of foregrounding.

According to Freeman (2000:253), a literary text is "the product of cognizing minds" and the process of a message decoding is "the product of other cognizing minds in the context of the physical and socio-cultural worlds in which they have been created and read"..Stockwell (2000:253) asserts that a reader turns to his/her background knowledge and relies on the life experience that facilitates the process of unraveling the hidden message, which a writer conveys through a literary text. This stylistic phenomenon arose linguists' interest and became one of the central and most debatable issues in modern linguistics.

Furthermore, cognitive-stylistic and pragmatic characteristics of semantic deviations as key mecha-

nisms of foregrounding have been researched separately. However, cognitive-stylistic and pragmatic characteristics of semantic deviations collectively have been superficially investigated or completely neglected so far. For this reason, it becomes the central focus of the research to be investigated and it is an attempt to fill the gap in it. Regarding Linguistic Pragmatics, the research will focus on investigating the language in use and the correspondence between semantic meaning of language, the context and the interlocutors. (Verdonk and Weber, 1995:13). Therefore, it becomes apparent that cognitive aspects and pragmatic aspects go hand in hand and in order to conduct effective research both aspects will be and have to be taken into consideration.

Cognitive and Pragmatic Aspects of Metaphor

Metaphor is regarded to be a common figure of speech in literature that serves the purpose for implementing semantic deviations in the literary text. To be more specific, integration of semantic deviations allows a writer to place particular information to the forefront on the semantic level, aka level of meaning. (Semino and Steen, 2008: 234). The usage of metaphor in the literary text allows a writer to encode a meaningful and logical message behind the combination of words that appear to be odd and illogical at first glance. (Short, 1996: 43). In order to unravel the implicit meaning a reader relies on verbal and nonverbal, perceptive and cognitive experience as well as he/she has to activate exploratory, emotional and evaluative activities, the cognitive structures and processes. One of the tools that plays an integral part in analyzing discourse is considered to be a concept. According to George Lakoff and Mark Johnson (1980:15), conceptual metaphor is not regarded to be a stylistic device exclusively, but it is predominantly based on “human systems” and “embodied experiences”. In order to decode the hidden meaning behind metaphor, a reader has to compare and contrast incompatible concepts integrated in the metaphor, draw parallel between them and spot the resemblance or similarity of the concepts.

Metaphor breaches the principle of selectional restrictions. To be more accurate, a writer integrates metaphor in the literary text in an attempt to communicate a message implicitly. It becomes apparent that the meaning of the phrase which incorporates metaphor is not direct and as long as a reader interprets it directly, he/she will fail to decode the genuine meaning of the message. Interpretation of the implicit meaning calls for encyclopedic knowledge and cultural background. Grice (1975/1989:34) states that the usage of metaphor also violates the maxim of quality. According to the maxim of quality, the information cannot be shared if it doesn't have “adequate evidence” or it is not true. Since a literary work doesn't necessarily has to be based on truth, and metaphors are not selected in accordance with logic, factual information or truth, once a reader comes to realize that a sentence is false, a writer induces him/her to decode the genuine meaning of the hidden message. John Searle (1979:70) puts forward a three-step process which a reader has to go through when he/she encounters metaphor: 1. Once a reader encounters an utterance, he/she is supposed to determine if a sentence incorporates metaphor or not, whether the

statement encompasses an apparent falsehood when taken literally. 2. Afterwards a reader identifies possible metaphorical values for the direct sentence by seeking ways how target domain has to do with source domain, or any distinctive features of source domain, when source domain is taken directly. 3. The reader then eliminates the series of potential metaphorical values to keep the relevant possible values in the context.

Cognitive and Pragmatic Aspects of Irony

To put it simply, Irony is deployed when a writer makes use of a statement with underlying meaning that is right the opposite of its literal meaning. By integrating irony into a literary text, a writer stimulates a reader's brain work to decode the hidden meanings behind the message being communicated. Consequently, interpretation of irony calls for scrutiny, meticulous analysis and intelligence. The usage of irony in speech or in a literary text allows a writer to place an emphasis on a value of depicted object significantly by accentuating something that is exact the opposite.

What is more, comparing and contrasting the genuine meaning of the message behind the ironic expression enables a reader to get a profound insight into a message conveyed by a writer. If a writer doesn't integrate irony into a literary work, the message will be communicated in a more economical and direct manner. From a reader's perspective, the decoding process of ironic expression will not call for extra effort and cognitive work. Consequently, comprehension of the context can facilitate the process of spotting and interpreting irony in a literary text.

On the one hand, the usage of sarcasm which falls into the category of verbal irony allows a writer to mock, express negative thoughts, disapproval or to tease when a situation doesn't go as it was initially expected by uttering of a statement with underlying meanings that is right the opposite of its literal meaning. Verbal irony enables a writer to convey an unpleasant or offensive message implicitly in a more polite and effective way. According to Leech, this is based on politeness principle. Or to be more accurate, it is about communicating an unpleasant or rude message in a more polite and indirect manner by means of implicatures so that an addressee doesn't find the message offensive.

According to Grice. (1989:90), the usage of irony violates the maxim of quality. According to the maxim of quality, the information cannot be shared if it doesn't have “adequate evidence” or if it is not true. Consequently, the usage of irony forces a reader to seek out a relevant proposition that will restore the application of the maxim. When it comes to irony, it is considered to be a statement with underlying meanings that is right the opposite of its literal meaning, which is regarded to be an implicature of the utterance. Finally, following conventional approaches of decoding irony doesn't always guarantee an adequate and accurate interpretation since ironic expression is not necessarily always based on an utterance with underlying meanings that accentuates right the opposite of its literal meaning. Relevance theory concerning irony involves a statement that is being utilized to metarepresent another representation it is similar with. What is more, a verbal irony can be im-

plemented by means of a figure of speech such as hyperbole where the related proposition is normally a weaker implicature, or understatement where the related proposition have a tendency to be a stronger implicature. When using hyperbole in a literary text, a writer more often than not communicates something that is less than it is literally uttered, which requires a reader to weaken the articulated message and make an inference of an implicature so as to restore the application of the maxim of quality to something that is considered to be true. As far as understatement goes, a writer more often than not communicates something that is more than it is literally uttered, which requires a reader to intensify what has been articulated in order to restore the application of the maxim of quality to something that is considered to be true.

Conceptual Metaphor

"Life is a game, boy. Life is a game that one plays according to the rules."

In the aforementioned sentence we can observe the usage of a conceptual metaphor. On the face of it, "life" and "game" are completely incompatible language means, but when reflecting on life matters we normally utilize game-related terms as well. For example, we take risks, we encounter and overcome obstacles, we learn lessons, we beat or win someone or end up failing living through wide range of experiences. This conceptual metaphor allows to interpret the entity of one kind through another one. To be more certain, the entity of "life" is understood through the entity of "game". Thus, "life" is a target domain, whereas "game" is a source domain. It is worthwhile to mention here that we decode the target domain, which is an abstract concept, by means of the source domain, which is a concrete thing and falls into a basis-level category.

1. ***"I could feel a terrific lecture coming on. I didn't mind the idea so much, but I didn't feel like being lectured to and smell Vicks Nose Drops and look at old Spencer in his pajamas and bathrobe all at the same time."***

2. ***"In New York, boy, money really talks--I'm not kidding."***

In the aforementioned extracts the usage of personification can be observed, which falls into the category of ontological metaphors. In the second extract "money" is perceived metaphorically as a tangible object. By referring to this item in this manner, the author indicates that "money" matters and plays an important role in New York City. The tangible inanimate object is perceived by the reader as a person. This enables the reader to get an insight into this very experience with nonhuman entities in terms of features that are typical of a human being. It raises the reader's awareness about the particular experience and allows him/her to get a more profound insight into the concept being depicted so that the reader could form an impression of it and comprehend it more deeply. (Скребуова, 2011, 39).

Container metaphor

"Jane Gallagher. Jesus . . . I couldn't get her off my mind. I really couldn't. I oughta go down and say hello to her, at least."

In the above-mentioned extract the usage of container metaphors can be displayed. According to

George Lakoff and Mark Johnson (1980:25), we tend to perceive our surrounding world or field of vision in the form of a container and conceptualize what we perceive as though it is in it. We are containers as human beings, who tend to be bordered by surface and an inner and outer orientation. Not only do we establish boundaries around our own bodies, but also we tend to conceptualize inner and outer orientation of other tangible objects. In the aforementioned examples "mind" can be seen as a container in which the main character, aka Holden, keeps his thoughts about the girl he is attracted to and cannot get rid of these thoughts. The aforementioned example functions as a condition that can be conceptualized in the form a container to allow the reader to get a better understanding of the condition being depicted in the novel. (Lakoff and Johnson, 2003:27)

From pragmatic perspectives, the aforementioned metaphors violate the maxim of quality. Once the reader comes to realize that the sentence is false, the writer induces him/her to decode the genuine meaning of the hidden message. The usage of metaphor violates the maxim of quality because it involves "misapplication of a term". This occurs since selection restrictions are violated by transforming inanimate objects such as "terrific lecture" and "money" into animate ones. In the fourth extract the integration of the metaphor violates the maxim of manner as well since the interpretation of the metaphor calls for the reader's brain work and efforts to unravel the implicit meaning. The usage of this metaphor is unnecessary according to the maxim of manner. If the writer had avoided using the metaphor, this would have made the literary text more clear and it would be easier for the reader to comprehend the content. For instance, the metaphor, *"I couldn't get her off my mind."* could be less ambiguous and sound more simple if the writer uttered this way "I couldn't stop thinking about her".

Irony

"What?" I said. Not too enthusiastic. He was always asking you to do him a big favor. You take a very handsome guy, or a guy that thinks he's a real hot-shot, and they're always asking you to do them a big favor. Just because they're crazy about themself, they think you're crazy about them, too, and that you're just dying to do them a favor. It's sort of funny, in a way."

In the above-mentioned extract irony is implemented where the main character, aka Holden, utilizes the statement that draws on the meaning that is right the opposite of its literal meaning. In the aforementioned example overstatement was utilized which falls into one of the categories of a verbal irony. The author depicts the inner feelings of the main character, aka Holden, to display that he is unwilling to do a favor when the guys at school who consider themselves as "hot-shot" demand something. The author is exaggerating or overstating the real condition that he intended to convey.

From pragmatic perspectives, since overstatement was utilized in the above-mentioned extract, the related proposition tends to be a weaker implicature. In this very situation the writer communicates the message less than it is literally uttered. Thus, it requires the

reader to weaken the articulated message and make an inference of the implicature so as to restore the application of the maxim of quality to the message that is considered to be true.

1. "He shoved my book back with his hand so that he could see the name of it. "Any good?" he said. **"This sentence I'm reading is terrific."** I can be quite sarcastic when I'm in the mood. He didn't get it, though. He started walking around the room again, picking up all my personal stuff, and Stradlater's. Finally, I put my book down on the floor. You couldn't read anything with a guy like Ackley around. It was impossible."

2. "This room stinks," I said. "I can smell your socks from way over here. Don'tcha ever send them to the laundry?" "If you don't like it, you know what you can do," Ackley said. **What a witty guy.** "How 'bout turning off the goddam light?"

3. The bellboy that showed me to the room was this very old guy around sixty-five. He was even more depressing than the room was. He was one of those bald guys that comb all their hair over from the side to cover up the baldness. I'd rather be bald than do that. **Anyway, what a gorgeous job for a guy around sixty-five years old. Carrying people's suitcases and waiting around for a tip.** I suppose he wasn't too intelligent or anything, but it was terrible anyway.

In the aforementioned sentences uttered by the main character of "The Catcher in the Rye" a verbal irony was deployed. By means of the verbal irony the writer communicates his unpleasant message indirectly. This way the writer induces the readers to analyze and decode the hidden meaning behind the message.

"What're ya gonna do--sleep in Ely's bed?" Ackley said. He was the perfect host, boy.

"I may. I may not. Don't worry about it." "I'm not worried about it. Only, I'd hate like hell if Ely came in all of a sudden and found some guy--"

"Relax. I'm not gonna sleep here. **I wouldn't abuse your goddam hospitality.**"

In the above-mentioned sentence we can observe the usage of sarcasm which is one type of a verbal irony. In the sentence the main character of "The Catcher in the Rye", Holden, emphasized that Ackley is not quite hospitable. This way the irony allows the

writer to place an emphasis on the value of the depicted object significantly by accentuating the meaning that is exactly the opposite. By integrating the irony into the message, the writer stimulates the reader's brain work to decode the hidden meanings being communicated. Consequently, the interpretation of the irony calls for the reader's scrutiny, meticulous analysis and intelligence. This enables the writer to convey the unpleasant or offensive message implicitly in a more polite and effective way.

From pragmatic perspectives, in the aforementioned extracts irony breaches the maxim of quality. Thus, the reader is forced to seek an appropriate proposition that will restore the application of the maxim. Concerning irony, the related proposition is a statement with underlying meanings that is right the opposite of its literal meaning, which is regarded to be an implicature of the utterance.

References

1. Grice, H.P. (1989). *Studies in the Way of Words*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
2. Leech G.N. (1969). *Alinguistic Guide to English poetry*. London: Longman.
3. Salinger J. D. (1991). *The Catcher in the Rye*. New York: Little, Brown and Company.
4. Searle J.R. (1979) *Expression and Meaning*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
5. Semino, E., Steen G. (2008). Metaphor in literature. In R. W. Gibbs, Jr. (Ed.), *The Cambridge handbook of metaphor and thought*. Cambridge University Press.
6. Short, M. (1996). *Exploring the language of poems, plays and prose*. London: Longman.
7. Stockwell P. (2002). *Cognitive Poetics: An Introduction*. London: Routledge.
8. Verdonk P., Weber J. (1995). *Twentieth-Century Fiction: From Text to Context*. London: Routledge.
9. Мукарежовский Я. (1967). Литературный язык и поэтический язык [Mukařovský, J. *Standard Language and poetic Language*] // Пражский лингвистический кружок. Москва: Прогресс. С. 406—431
10. Шкловский В.Б. (1919). Искусство как прием [Shklovsky V.B. *Art as a Technique*] // Поэтика. Петроград: 18-ая Гос. типография. С. 13—26.